

A Novel Design Variation of a Monolithically Integrated SiC Circuit Breaker

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Abstract—This paper provides a thorough design study of a two-pole solid-state circuit breaker (SSCB) device for 900 V DC applications supported by quasi-static two-dimensional TCAD simulations. Building on the work of Boettcher et al. using 4H-SiC JFET technology with monolithic integration of an n-channel JFET (nJFET) and a p-channel JFET (pJFET), the proposed design replaces the horizontal nJFET with a vertical structure [1-3]. This change eliminates the need for a second epitaxial layer and reduces the number of ion implantation steps from six to three, thereby simplifying the manufacturing process. Numerical TCAD simulations reveal that the novel SSCB design enables independent tuning of threshold and breakdown voltage. In the pJFET, adjustments in channel depth and doping concentration allow the blocking voltage window to be enhanced from 450 V to over 800 V, while maintaining a breakdown voltage of approx. 900 V. These findings indicate that the proposed SSCB design offers improved performance and fabrication efficiency for high voltage DC applications.

Keywords—SiC, circuit breaker, SSCB, device design, TCAD, monolithic integration, JFET, 900 V, power electronics

I. INTRODUCTION

Power electronic devices play a crucial role in modern electrical systems, where fast and reliable protection is essential to prevent damage from short circuits or overcurrent conditions. In this context, solid-state circuit breakers (SSCB) offer a promising alternative to traditional mechanical circuit breakers due to their fast response and reliability [4]. In Fig. 1 (a), the equivalent circuit diagram of the proposed self-controlled SSCB is shown. It relies on monolithic integration of an n-channel JFET (nJFET) and a p-channel JFET (pJFET). In this configuration, the drain-source voltage (V_{DS}) of one JFET is equal to the gate-source voltage (V_{GS}) of the other JFET, enabling the intrinsic current controlled blocking mechanism.

The original SSCB design was introduced and fabricated by Boettcher et al., who reported a reaction time of 52 ns and a cut-off time of 122 ns in response to a short-circuit event at 800 V DC link voltage [2, 5, 6]. In their design, the channels of both JFETs are horizontally oriented, necessitating a regrowth of a second epitaxial layer followed by a dry etching mesa process to create the nJFET gate structure. This paper presents a novel SSCB design, which reduces the number ion implantation steps from six to three and, furthermore, eliminates the need for an additional epitaxial layer.

Figure 1: SSCB equivalent circuit diagram (a) and schematic output characteristics (b).

The schematic output characteristics of the proposed SSCB are shown in Fig. 1 (b). The anode current density (J_A) increases with the anode-cathode voltage (V_{AK}) until a certain trigger current density (J_{trig}) is reached. When the current density drops below 10^{-5} A/cm², per definition, the threshold voltage (V_{th}) is reached, and the current flow is considered blocked. This threshold corresponds to approx. seven orders of magnitude lower than the maximum trigger current observed in the simulations conducted in this study. With a further increase in V_{AK} , the current flow is blocked until breakdown occurs. In the original design, a reach-through mechanism in the gate structures is observed at a high blocking voltage (s. Fig. 1 (b), blue line), whereas in the novel design, avalanche is the dominant breakdown mechanism (s. Fig. 1 (b), black line) [3, 6, 7]. To analyse the proposed device, Sentaurus TCAD software was utilized, employing the sProcess, SDE, and sDevice tools.

Figure 2: The cell structures of the nJFET, pJFET (top) and proposed novel SSCB (bottom) presented in this work.

II. CELL STRUCTURES

The cell structures of the nJFET, pJFET, and the novel SSCB design are illustrated in Fig. 2. The proposed device architecture is based on an epitaxial layer with a thickness of $9.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a nitrogen doping concentration of $8 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. In general, ion implantation of N and Al are utilized to create additional n- and p- regions, respectively. The first suggested fabrication step involves a p-type implantation (“p-Impl.”) to form the gate and source regions of the nJFET, as well as the source and drain regions of the pJFET. In the proposed SSCB design, these implantations can be carried out in a single process step. The “n-source” implantation for the nJFET and the p-channel implantation (“p-Ch.”) for the pJFET complete the cell formation. A key advantage of the proposed fabrication process over the original approach is the reduction of ion implantation steps from six to three, as well as the elimination of the second epitaxial layer growth and the mesa dry etching process. As the JFET cells are interconnected to form the SSCB, the electrical contacts are redefined: instead of drain, source, and gate, these are referred to as anode, cathode, and the floating source terminal, respectively.

A. Design Parameters

For a more detailed analysis of the proposed SSCB, a comprehensive understanding of the JFET behaviour is essential. Therefore, a design parameter study on the JFET characteristics is conducted using a reference parameter set listed in Tab. 1. Based on the simulation data obtained for the JFETs, specific SSCB structures are designed. Three variations of the novel design with varying pJFET design parameters are investigated, which differ solely in channel depth (d_{pCh}) and channel doping concentration ($N_{A,pCh}$). The nJFET parameters as well as the pJFET channel length (l_{pCh}) remain identical across all designs of the novel SSCB. For better comparison, the parameter set of the original SSCB design is also provided in Tab. 1.

B. Numerical Simulations

Although the modelled cell structures are created in SDE, Monte Carlo simulations in sProcess are used to obtain more realistic implantation profiles. The resulting profiles shown in Fig. 3 (a) are imported to SDE as elaborated in [8]. For all SSCB designs, the maximum energy used in the Monte Carlo simulations is 540 keV.

Table 1: Reference parameter set for the JFETs as well as the design parameters for the novel and original design of the proposed SSCB.

Channel	n-Channel			p-Channel			
	Parameter	l_{nCh} (μm)	d_{nCh} (μm)	$N_{D,nCh}$ (cm^{-3})	l_{pCh} (μm)	d_{pCh} (μm)	$N_{A,pCh}$ (cm^{-3})
nJFET		2	2	$8e15$	-	-	-
pJFET		-	-	-	1.8	0.7	$1e17$
SSCB novel design 1		1.1	1.8	$8e15$	3	0.2	$1e17$
SSCB novel design 2		1.1	1.8	$8e15$	3	0.4	$5e16$
SSCB novel design 3		1.1	1.8	$8e15$	3	0.6	$5e16$
SSCB original design		1	0.5	$1e17$	1.8	0.55	$5e17$

Figure 3: SSCB doping profiles (a) and nJFET output characteristics (b), drain current density over channel length (c) and channel depth (d).

In the simulations, the depth of the “p-Ch.” doping profile is scaled to adjust d_{pCh} , whereas a deeper “p-Impl.” profile results in a longer n-channel (i.e. higher l_{nCh}). Accordingly, the arrangement of the doped regions defines d_{nCh} and l_{pCh} . The impact of these variations on specific operating points is analysed using simulation in sDevice emphasizing two distinct differences in the electrical characteristics compared to the original design: the nJFET output characteristics and the pJFET transfer characteristics.

1) nJFET

Since the general purpose of a SSCB is to carry the entire load current, minimising its resistance is essential. In case of the proposed SSCB, this correlates with a high on-state current density [1, 7]. Fig. 3 (b) shows the output characteristic of the nJFET for both designs at a V_{GS} bias of 0 V. The nJFET in the original design reaches saturation at $V_{DS} \approx 15$ V. In the novel design, saturation does not occur before 100 V. Due to design implications of the novel nJFET, the doping concentration is an order of magnitude lower than for the original design. Thus, the on-state resistance is significantly higher, as can be observed from the linear region of the curves. Fig. 3 (c) illustrates the decrease in J_D with increasing l_{nCh} at $V_{DS} = 100$ V, while Fig. 3 (d) shows the rise in J_D with increasing d_{nCh} . Hence, to achieve high current density, a short and deep n-channel is necessary. For channel depths below 1.2 μm , the n-channel becomes normally-off (i.e. at $V_{GS} = 0$ V). Regarding the variation of doping concentration in the nJFET channel region, an additional n-type ion implantation or a variation of the donor concentration pose feasible options. As additional implantation steps are not favoured within this study and a variation in epitaxial layer doping concentration would in turn affect the breakdown voltage of the SSCB, these options are not pursued further.

Figure 4: Transfer characteristics (a), DIBL factor correlation (b) and electric field enhancement in the cell (c) of the novel pJFET.

2) pJFET

Fig. 4 (a) shows the transfer characteristic of the novel pJFET for the reference parameter set and a drain bias of $V_{DS} = -50$ mV. A rather high V_{Th} of approx. 700 V can be observed. At approx. 1250 V the gate structure breaks down due to avalanche (s. V_{Break}). Thus, a large off-state window of 550 V is obtained. As depicted in Fig. 4 (b), V_{Th} decreases with l_{pCh} indicating the impact of short channel effects. For quantification, a similar method to determining the drain-induced barrier lowering (DIBL) factor (γ) is applied. It is calculated from the change in threshold voltage with varying drain voltage as given in Eq. 1 [9].

$$\gamma = -\frac{\Delta V_{Th}}{\Delta V_D} \quad (1)$$

As can be obtained from Fig. 4 (b), at $l_{pCh} = 1.7$ μm γ has a value of approx. 10 and decreases with l_{pCh} . Based on the results, l_{pCh} of higher than 3 μm is required to mitigate the influence of this short channel effect. It is particularly pronounced because the “p-Impl.” regions are shielding the p-channel from the electric field propagating from the anode through the epitaxial layer. Fig. 4 (c) shows the pJFET region at 800 V for l_{pCh} equal to 1.8 μm and 3.0 μm , respectively, emphasizing electric field enhancement at the “p-Impl.” regions. As can be observed, for longer channels, the local maximum of the electric field increases. Additionally, the electric field reaches further into the “p-Ch.” region and, thus, depleting the channel. This is a result of less electrostatic shielding, which ultimately causes the gate to lose control over the p-channel region.

Compared to the original design, the pJFET in the novel SSCB architecture does not include a backgate, as the second epitaxial layer has been eliminated. Thus, reach-through as a mechanism for gate breakdown does not occur in the novel design and, therefore, avalanche breakdown is the only relevant breakdown mechanism. In contrast to

Figure 5: Novel pJFET threshold voltage and breakdown voltage for varying channel doping concentration (a), length (b) and depth (c).

reach-through, avalanche is not influenced by pJFET design parameters (i.e. l_{pCh} , d_{pCh} and $N_{A,pCh}$). Consequently, V_{Th} and V_{Break} can be independently designed to maximize the off-state window as shown in Fig. 5. For higher values of $N_{A,pCh}$ (a) and d_{pCh} (c) V_{Th} increases since a higher potential is required to extend the space-charge region across the entire channel. Conversely, for higher values of l_{pCh} (b) V_{Th} decreases due to less electrostatic shielding. Although avalanche breakdown is mainly determined by thickness and doping concentration of the epitaxial layer, a slight reduction of V_{Break} can be observed in Fig. 5 (b). As discussed before, higher values of l_{pCh} lead to more pronounced field enhancement and a higher local maximum of the electric field. Therefore, the critical electric field at the edges of the “p-Impl.” regions is reached at lower values of V_{AK} . The ability to independently scale V_{Th} and V_{Break} makes the proposed SSCB design approach suitable to address low-voltage applications, while maintaining the capability to withstand higher voltages.

C. Proposed Solid-State Circuit Breaker

The structure of the proposed SSCB created in SDE is shown in Fig. 6. The image in the top illustrates the doping concentration, while the bottom images emphasize the current flow in on-state and during avalanche breakdown, respectively. In on-state, the current flows from the anode through the nJFET and source. Subsequently, through the pJFET to the cathode. If V_{AK} is increased further, the proposed SSCB blocks the current until, eventually, V_{Break} is reached and the current flows directly from the anode through the epitaxial layer to the cathode. The unique blocking functionality of the proposed SSCB requires depletion of both JFET channels. In the original design, this is induced by clamping V_{SK} to the saturation voltage of the nJFET [3, 7]. Thus, V_{AS} , which is identical to $V_{GS,pJFET}$, increases with V_{AK} resulting in depletion of the p-channel.

Figure 6: Structure of the TCAD model indicating doping concentration (top), and current flow in on-state and during avalanche (bottom).

Figure 7: Source-cathode voltage (V_{SK}) over V_{AK} for the novel and original design of the proposed SSCB (a) and V_{SK} over anode-source voltage (V_{AS}) illustrating the difference in pinch-off behavior.

However, as shown in Fig. 3 (b), no saturation of the novel nJFET is observed for a wide voltage range, which leads to additional challenges with respect to the SSCB design. Fig. 7 (a) shows the course of the floating source potential (V_{SK}) over V_{AK} . As shown in Fig. 1 (a), V_{SK} is equal to $V_{GS,nJFET}$ and $V_{DS,pJFET}$. The distinct kink at approx. 20 V in the $V_{SK,SSCB}$ -curve of the original design indicates the nJFET saturation. In contrast, V_{SK} of the novel design increases steadily until approx. 180 V. Fig. 7 (b) shows V_{SK} over the anode-source voltage (V_{AS}) of the novel SSCB. Referring to Fig. 1 (a), V_{AS} is equal to $V_{DS,nJFET}$ and $V_{GS,pJFET}$. Therefore, in the proposed SSCB configuration, pJFET channel depletion (i.e. $V_{Th,pJFET,SSCB}$) is obtained as soon as $V_{SK,SSCB}$ reaches the value of $V_{Th,pJFET}$. As illustrated by the curve for $V_{SK,pJFET}$ in Fig. 7 (b), $V_{Th,pJFET}$ continuously increases with V_{AS} due to short channel effects and electrostatic shielding as discussed earlier. Eventually, at the intersection of the two graphs, $V_{GS,pJFET}$ reaches $V_{Th,pJFET}$. Consequently, the p-channel is depleted and the SSCB turns to blocking state.

Obviously, the absence of a clamping mechanism for V_{SK} in combination with the electrostatic shielding of the pJFET gate results in higher $V_{Th,pJFET}$. This effect is undesired, since it limits the design freedom for a parameter set, where V_{Th} is reached before V_{Break} . A rather long p-channel is required, to avoid a V_{Th} -shift to higher values, which would become apparent in a smaller slope of $V_{Th,pJFET}$ in Fig. 7 (b).

Figure 8: Output characteristics of the proposed SSCB compared to the original design.

Fig. 8 illustrates the electrical characteristics of three distinct structures from the novel design alongside a comparable structure from the original SSCB design. It should be noted, that the pJFET dominates the total resistance of the SSCB. Since the p-channel in the novel design is twice as long as in the original design, a higher resistance is obtained. Therefore, the maximum value of J_{trig} in the novel design is lower. Furthermore, J_{trig} decreases with a reduced V_{Th} , while V_{Break} remains almost unchanged. The slight deviation observed in V_{Break} can be attributed to variations in channel depth, which slightly affect the electric field distribution in device cell. As a result, the blocking voltage window, which is defined as the difference between V_{Break} and V_{Th} , can be enhanced from 450 V to over 800 V for a breakdown voltage of approx. 900 V.

III. SUMMARY

In this study, a novel 4H-SiC SSCB design based on integrated nJFET and pJFET structures is introduced, emphasizing both process simplification and aspects of device performance compared to the original design demonstrated by Boettcher et al. [1-3]. A significant advantage of the proposed approach is the reduction in fabrication complexity achieved by performing p-type implantations for forming the gate, source, and drain regions in a single process step. This innovation reduces the total number of ion implantation steps from six to three and removes the need for an additional epitaxial layer growth and a subsequent mesa dry etching step. A comprehensive simulation study using Sentaurus TCAD was conducted to assess the electrical behaviour of both the nJFET and the pJFET. The design of the novel nJFET implies a longer channel with a lower doping concentration. This results in an increase in resistance compared to the original design, leading to a reduction in current density and a delayed onset of saturation. In contrast, the novel pJFET allows for an independent design of threshold and gate breakdown voltage by varying channel depth and doping concentration, which

facilitates a marked increase in the blocking voltage window from 450 V to over 800 V while maintaining a breakdown voltage of approx. 900 V. Moreover, the paper details the interaction between the nJFET and pJFET in the SSCB configuration, highlighting the role of electrostatic shielding and channel dimensions in current blocking performance. Overall, the proposed SSCB design not only streamlines the fabrication process but also offers enhanced electrical characteristics, rendering it a promising candidate for applications that require efficient low-voltage blocking combined with high-voltage tolerance.

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